

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B126
Date: 07 Sep 2005
Take Off 09:56:45
Landing: 14:57:16
Flight Time 5hr00m31

Campaign: AMPEP
Operating Area: Coastal UK SW to Humberside

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Ute Skiba	CEH
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	CCN/CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
7	Filters	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	Filters Training	Alison Perry	FAAM
9	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
10	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
11	Bag sample 1	Debbie Polson	CEH
12	Bag sample 2	Chiara di Marco	CEH
13	AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University
14	WAS	Jimmy Hopkins	York
15	PTRMS	Jennifer Murphy	UEA
16	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B126 Track 07-SEP-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b126
 Date: 07 September 2005
 Project: AMPEP
 Location: UK coast, SW to Newcastle

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
092548		INU to nav	0.39 kft	127	
095645		T/O	1.4 kft	358	cranfield
100647	102056	Run 1.1	10.0 kft	243	fl100 NOxy cals
100925		Nev and JW zeros	10.0 kft	244	
101022		video recording	10.0 kft	244	ffc and dfc started
103631	103732	Run 2.1	6.0 kft	229	fl60
103743	103948	Profile 1	6.0 - 4.0 kft	229	fl60 > 4000ft
103948	104051	Run 3.1	4.0 kft	229	4000ft
104052	104300	Profile 2	4.0 - 2.0 kft	229	4000ft - 2000ft
104301	104405	Run 4.1	2.0 kft	229	2000ft
104406	104517	Profile 3	2.0 - 1.0 kft	229	2000ft - 1000ft
104518	105359	Run 5.1	1.0 kft	228	qnh 1013 wp48 - 46
110834	112617	Run 6.1	0.99 - 0.98 kft	138	crossing coast - wp46 - wp45
110923		core chem cal	0.97 kft	137	
111101		wp46	0.95 kft	114	wp46
111254		nev zero JW zero	0.97 kft	088	
111327		new video tapes	0.98 kft	089	
111705		left hand video u/s	0.98 kft	092	only recording ffc
112727	114122	Run 6.2	0.99 - 0.97 kft	046	wp45 - wp44
114123	115659	Run 6.3	0.97 kft	079	wp44 - wp43
115659	120902	Run 6.4	0.97 - 0.95 kft	082	wp43 - wp42
120902	122218	Run 6.5	0.95 - 0.94 kft	039	wp42 - wp41
120919		core chem cal	0.98 kft	007	
121158		ffc video changed	0.98 kft	011	
122219	123909	Run 6.6	1.0 kft	355	wp41 - wp40
123909	124513	Run 6.7	1.0 kft	303	wp40 - wp87
124514	130424	Run 6.8	1.0 kft	299	wp87 - wp80
125030		qnh 1012			
125949		qnh 1011			
130425	132054	Run 6.9	1.0 - 1.1 kft	315	wp80 - wp79
130900		qnh 1009			
131708		qnh 1008			
132055	132927	Run 6.10	1.1 - 1.2 kft	327	wp79 - extension north to exit plume
132928	133037	Profile 4	1.2 - 2.1 kft	337	1000ft - 2000ft
133111	133141	Run 7.1	2.1 kft	337	2000ft
133142	133345	Profile 5	2.2 - 4.0 kft	338	2000ft - 4000ft
133345	133445	Run 8.1	4.0 kft	334	4000ft
133631	133814	Profile 6	4.0 - 6.0 kft	162	4000ft - fl60
133815	134735	Run 9.1	6.0 - 5.9 kft	166	fl60
134957	140601	Run 10,1	1.4 - 1.1 kft	151	wp79 - wp80
140601	142551	Run 10.2	1.1 kft	149	wp80 - wp87
140621		qnh 1009			
141149		qnh 1010			
143012	144500	Run 11.1	10.0 kft	156	fl100 cal run
145716		Land			Cranfield
		gps			52'04.36N 000'37.5W
		inu			52'01.80N 000'37.55W

B126 Track 07-SEP-05

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B126

Mission Scientist: Ute Skiba, CEH

Date : 06-September-2005

Outline schedule:

07:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
09:00 – Briefing
10:15 – Clear aircraft and security check
10:30 – Doors close
11:00 – Take off Cranfield
16:00 – Land Cranfield
16:30 – Debrief
18:30 – Power down

Location: A coastal transect of the South and East Coast of England

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols leaving the UK in gentle North Westerly airflow over the UK. The objective, in addition to measuring the export fluxes of pollutants is to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be obtained by flying off the South and East coasts along a coastal transect. After transit to the Bristol Channel, some boundary layer air (1000 ft) will be sampled before crossing Cornwall and sampling along the Channel coast. The transect of the UK outflow begins along the English Channel heading East to Dover then North as far as the fuel capacity allows, while avoiding to refuel. The vertical structure of concentrations and meteorological parameters will be assessed during (a) a descending vertical profiles (6000 to 50 ft) upwind when descending into the English Channel, and (b) an ascending vertical profile following U-turn (into wind) at most northerly point. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO). The measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

- a) Take off Cranfield 09:00 and climb to 10000 ft for transit east to operating area. Destination waypoint 47 in the Bristol Channel; background filter run (sampling!) & NO_x calibration. Some background bags.
- b) T+20: Fast descend to 1000 ft on reaching the Bristol channel, start of continuous bag sampling.
- c) T+30: crossing Cornwall at 1000ft or lowest possible altitude
- d) T+40: on reaching English Channel, vertical profile for sampling the boundary layer structure off the coast with 1 min sampling at each height (6000, 4000, 2000, 500, 100, 50). This will be a descending or ascending profile, depending on the height at which the transect of Cornwall occurs.
- e) T+55: Return to 1000 ft. 30-minute filter pack runs from here (called by Mission Scientist)
- f) T+ 200 U-turn in front of Firth of Forth, downwind profile up (50, 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000). Re-sample East Coast, heading South.
- g) T+ 300 Land Cranfield

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 -
2. Pilot 2 -
3. CCM -
4. Core Chemistry – Doug Anderson
5. Cloud Physics – Martyn Pickering
6. Flight Manager – Jim Crawford
7. Mission Scientist – Ute Skiba
8. Filters- Stuart Heat
9. Filters training – Alison Perry
10. CCM/CCM2 – Paul James
11. Bag Sampling 1 – Debbie Polson
12. Bag Sampling 2 – Chiara di Marco
13. AMS – Jonny Crosier
14. WAS – Jimmy Hopkins
15. PTRMS – Jennifer Murphy
16. NOxy – Dave Stewart

- Transit to Bristol Channel
- Profile down to point 37
- 48 50:50N 4:40W
- 46 50:01N 3:25W
- 45 50:01N 2:00W
- 44 50:40N 1:00W
- 43 50:40N 0:30E
- 42 51:05N 1:30E
- 41 51:53N 1:47E
- 40 52:41N 1:47E
- 39 52:00N 1:30E
- 80 54:05N 0:05E
- 79 50:00N 1:10W
- 76 (fuel permitting)
- 79 50:00N 1:10W
- 80 54:05N 0:05E
- 39 52:00N 1:30E
- Cranfield

Init : Tue,06SEP2005 06Z

Valid: Wed,07SEP2005 12Z

10m Wind (kt)

Daten: GFS-Modell des amerikanischen Wetterdienstes
(C) Wetterzentrale
www.wetterzentrale.de

CO Concentration field as predicted for 07/09/05 by the NAME model

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO_3 & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH_3). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value. Three 30-min runs of filters on each leg (S→N and N→ S)

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO_2 , NO and NO_2 will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at FL10.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to

maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

PTRMS: Operation as normal.

NO_{xy}: Operation as normal; calibration during transits at FL100

WAS: Sampling density and location to be decided.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂: Not available..

Quick-look data: pressure height, lat, long, temp, RH, CN, SO₂, NO, NO₂, O₃, CO, NO_{xy}(HNO₃)

Mission Scientist's Log

Ute Skisa

Flight No **B.126**.....

Date **7-9-05**.....

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Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:00:50				No profile ^{Today} below 1000 feet. start at Cranfield light wind broken clouds & sunny
10:00 ~	1			NOx calibration
10:36:31	P1	6000	Bristol Channel	start profile descending
		wind	11 ms ⁻¹	237° very light cloud
10:39:48	P2	4000		
10:40:10 ~	P3 ^{Run 41}	2000		245°C / 285 W speed 8 m s ⁻¹
10:45:07	P4 ^{Run 51}	1000		221° 7 m s ⁻¹
		keep at 1000 until	point 48	
10:46 ~		some cloud on	right,	turned to wards coast to avoid cloud.
		over head very	little cloud.	
		End of run	5.1	at 1000
10:53 ~	Run 6	at 5000		
12:10 ~				entered English Channel. at WP towards WP46
12:10	FPI	start filters and bag samples @ 1 min intervals @ 30 min intervals.		
12:10	~	WP 46		Wind 3 m s ⁻¹ 228°
		one video camera broken		no more downward
12:15	becoming			
		sea calm, hazy		
		Force 1?		
12:25	AMS	increased aerogel from shipping (also SO ₂)		
12:26	WP45	now turn back ^{and fly towards} coast.		

Mission Scientist's Log

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Flight No **B.126**.....

Date **7-9-05**.....

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BST GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	on route	WP45 - 44		hazy	inversion, possibly flying on top
		of an inversion		WS	2ms ⁻¹ 255°C
12:30		SO ₂	still high		
12:40	Filter pack 2		2		
	↓			since 11:15	slight increases in NO _x SO ₂
	almost @	WP44		still hazy	3-4ms ⁻¹ 241°C
				grey / yellowish.	
12:55		close to	Eastborne	6ms ⁻¹	slightly less hazy
				still can see a layer of protection ahead.	261°
12:57		Hastings		turn	in at WP 43
13:03		small amount of fog underneath us		generally	
		still hazy		WS now	8ms ⁻¹ 216°, some sheets of cloud + SWiflow roller overhead
13:05		now more fog		below	
13:06		nile orange haze underneath			
		land not clearly visible.			
		cliffs of Dover =>		lots of fog =>	fog below
13:00	Filter pack 3			will start shortly +	some calc. calibration
13:12		Wind	no	10ms ⁻¹	203° we are in
	Ramsfote.	cloud / fog.		poor	visibility
13:20	above	cloudy & foggy		11ms ⁻¹	215°
13:25	the wash	12	ms ⁻¹	208°	a bit clearer.
					small increase in NO _x , SO ₂ , CO ₂
13:30	approaching	wind fan.			NO _x peak finished now.

WP40

Mission Scientist's Log

UTC

Flight No **B.126**.....

Date **7-9-05**.....

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BST GMT	Run/ Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:35				slight turbulence	clear now
				still in plane.	
12:40				slight turbulence	
~ WP 87		12:44		Lower plane completed.	WS 9ms ⁻¹
12:56	Filter pack 4		4		2140
	↑			cloudy/hazy	WS 9ms ⁻¹
12:55		6 feet		slight dips	downwind.
:57		NOx plane.			
13:00		sharp rise in CO ₂		SO ₂ NOx =	
13:02	WP 80	big NOx plane		also SO ₂ NOx	
				wind 7ms ⁻¹	235
13:10	Filter pack 5			changed in mid of high pollution	
				wind 5ms ⁻¹	clearer dense cloud
		over head		NOx + CO	
					NOx ↑
		NOx graph from beginning			
		CO graph similar.			
13:25		heading towards WP 78		NOx decreasing	stability.
13:39:28	P4	profile run started			
		stop FP 5			
13:31:42	P5	in broken cloud.		13ms ⁻¹	242°
		turn bad at Furn Islands.		at 6000 feet	
		LOO stop			
13:45		bad down to		1000 feet	in bad down count

Mission Scientist Debrief for flight B126 7 September 2005

Objective of flight:

As stated in sortie brief for flight B126

Time: 10:50 BST depart Cranfield and 16:00 BST return to Cranfield

Weather conditions:

Wind directions ranged from 203 to 255⁰ and did not change much throughout the flight. The wind speed was very low in the English Channel, typically 3 m s⁻¹ and low-level clouds and fog impaired visibility. The coast remained hidden behind clouds for most of the travel through the English Channel and we dipped in and out of this layer of inversion. The fog eventually lifted, as we turned into the North Sea and close to Ramsgate wind speeds increased to 10 m s⁻¹. It remained cloudy throughout this flight.

Flight route

This did not really deviate from the planned route (Cranfield – Bristol Channel-over Cornwall- English Channel- North Sea to Waypoint 78. Profiles, i.e. sampling at 6000, 4000, 2000 and 1000 feet were carried out twice, once in the Bristol Channel and then again in the North Sea, once the pollution plume from the Newcastle area waned off. Flight below 1000 feet was not possible due to problems with the aircraft software updates. The remaining time a height of 1000 feet was kept.

Science

The goals of this flight were achieved as well as possible under the circumstances of very low windspeeds and inversion in the English Channel and the inability to decent to heights of less than 1000 feet.

Plumes of CO, NO_x, SO₂ were clearly visible northwesterly from London and the Newcastle region. On the return journey the large NE plume was slightly clipped (Middleburgh plume was missing), otherwise concentrations mirror imaged the outward journey. Filterpacks were taken at roughly 30 min intervals; no instrument problems were recorded, apart from lack of NO₂ calibration on the return journey.

Prepared by Ute Skiba

Handwritten draft on 7.9.05

Word.doc apart from the last 4 lines and cosmetic treatment on 19.9.05

Word.doc final version 11.2.06

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B126

Date: 08/09/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:36:31											Start Run 2. 1 @ FL060
10:37:00	70	0.06	1								
10:37:36											End of Run 2.1 Start Profile 1
10:38:43	60	0.06	1								FL050
10:39:51											End of P1 start Run 3.1 @ FL040
10:40:00	80	0.06									
10:40:51											End of Run 3.1 Start Profile 2
10:41:53	110	0.06		5							FL030
10:43:15											End of P2 start R 4.1 @ @2000'
10:44:00	70	0.07									
10:44:05											End of Run 4.1 start Profile 3
10:45:10	230	0.08		10							End of P 3 Start Run 5.1 @ 1000'
10:46:00	200	0.07		10							
10:48:00	380	0.07		10							
10:50:00	160	0.08		10							
10:52:00	160	0.08		10							
10:54:00											End of Run 5.1
11:08:35											Start Run 6.1 @ 1000'
11:09:00	380	0.09		5							
11:11:00	760	0.07		5							
11:13:00	360	0.09		10							
11:15:00	350	0.09		5							
11:17:00	530	0.08		5							
11:19:00	450	0.09		10							
11:21:00	480	0.08		10							
11:23:00	800	0.08		10							
11:25:00	1200	0.08	2	10							
11:27:00	560	0.08		10							
11:29:00	400	0.08		10							
11:31:00	1125	0.08		10							
11:33:00	1100	0.09		10							
11:35:00	1050	0.08		10							
11:37:00	1050	0.08		5							
11:39:00	700	0.08		10							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B126

Date: 08/09/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:41:00	1800	0.08	2	10							
11:43:00	680	0.09		10							
11:45:00	1300	0.09		5							
11:47:00	1200	0.08		10							
11:49:00	1165	0.08									
11:51:00	860	0.08	3	10							
11:53:00	620	0.08		5							
11:55:00	450	0.08		10							
11:57:00	400	0.08		10							
11:59:00	380	0.08		5							
12:01:00	500	0.08		5							
12:03:00	435	0.09		5							
12:05:00	490	0.09		5							
12:07:00	720	0.09		5							
12:09:00	920	0.09		5							
12:11:00	950	0.09		5							SID2 fail, not restarted
12:13:00	1050	0.09		5							
12:15:00	1150	0.09		5							
12:17:00	1600	0.09		5							
12:19:00	1800	0.09		5							
12:21:00	1300	0.09		10							
12:23:00	620	0.09		10							
12:25:00	430	0.08		5							
12:27:00	580	0.08	4	5							
12:29:00	380	0.08		10							
12:31:00	400	0.08		5							
12:33:00	400	0.08		5							
12:35:00	640	0.08		10							
12:37:00	800	0.07		5							
12:39:00	610	0.07		5							
12:41:00	800	0.07		5							
12:43:00	620	0.07		5							
12:45:00	540	0.08		10							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B126

Date: 08/09/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	
12:47:00	700	0.08	4	5							
12:49:00	700	0.09	5	10							
12:51:00	580	0.09		10							
12:53:00	750	0.09		5							
12:55:00	630	0.08		10							
12:57:00	640	0.08		10							
12:59:00	640	0.08		5							
13:01:00	760	0.08		5							
13:03:00	525	0.08		5							
13:05:00	675	0.08		5							
13:07:00	720	0.08		5							
13:09:00	770	0.09		10							
13:11:00	800	0.09		10							
13:13:00	910	0.09		5							
13:15:00	900	0.09		5							
13:17:00	660	0.09		5							
13:19:00	430	0.07	6	5							
13:21:00	390	0.08		5							
13:23:00	325	0.08		5							
13:25:00	310	0.08		3							
13:27:00	340	0.08		5							
13:29:28											End of Run 6.1 Start Profile 4
13:30:38											End of P2 start Run 7.1 @ 2000'
13:31:00	250	0.08		5							
13:31:46											End Run 7.1 Start Profile 5
13:32:48	200	0.12	38	1000							3000'
13:33:49											End of P5 Start Run 8.1 @ 4000'
13:34:00	200	0.08	75	1000							
13:34:47											End of Run 8.1
13:36:31											Start Profile 6 from 4000'
13:37:29	110	0.10	172	10	2	800	800	50	1200	1	5000'
13:38:22	70	0.07		10	2	800	800	280	1000	1	End of P6 start Run 9.1 @ 6000'
13:47:35											End of Run 9.1

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No: B126

Date: 07/09/05

Operator: AP

Run No	Disk No 1	Disk No 2	Disk No 3	Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
B/ground	136	86	115	top	10.37z	10.50z		417*	Teflon
B/ground	148	85	114	bottom	10.37z	10.50z		214*	Teflon/Nylon/Paper
1	152	128	93	top	11.08z	11.42z		1091*	
1	150	117	155	bottom	11.08z	11.42z		561*	
2	157	96	56	top	11.46z	12.10z		770*	
2	94	125	16	bottom	11.46z	12.10z		396*	
3	53	119	118	Top	12.13z	12.44z		992*	
3	141	132	5	Bottom	12.13z	12.44z		613*	
4	98	112	97	top	12.50z	13.12z		704*	
4	54	92	18	bottom	12.50z	13.12z		363*	
5	N/A	149	145	Top	13.15z	13.30z		480*	
5	91	120	10	bottom	13.15z	13.30z		247*	
6	156	135	147	Top	13.50z	14.30z		1280*	
6	129	146	58	Bottom	13.50z	14.30z		660*	

*Note these Accumulated Volumes are a best estimate from previous AMPEP Flights

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B126**Date:** 07/09/2005

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B126.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B126.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B126.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B126.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B126_seadas.dat iii) exit	13/03/06	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written Complete, no errors 38564 blocks read / written
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B126 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B126_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	15/11/05	complete
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B126 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec Preparation of imagery for Core data product iii) WAVE> auto_image		This section is optional

a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B126 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B126_2Dx_IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter	16/11/05	Complete. files are in
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		O:\CloudPhysics Core data
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO a) Flight number: B126 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data 0	0	As noted in operator log
e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B126_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unkdown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B126_PROC2D	132000 135000 11 2	Note the particle type
10) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B126_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B126_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	13/03/06	complete
11) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B126_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B126_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	13/03/06	complete

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B126

Date: 07/09/2005

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC				
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments		
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC				
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults				
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:B126_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B126.nc]	13/03/06	Defaults in [square brackets] As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated		
2) Ftp transfer to BADC				
- stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B126.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B126.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B126_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary			13/03/06	complete

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" outdir:B126_PMSDATA.zip PMSDATA:B126*.* Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.	13/03/06	Note destination directory "outdir" Outdir= CLOUD_PHYS:[BROWN.PMSZIP]

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B126**Date:** 07/09/2005

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC B126_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B126_FFSSP_HVMS.txt B126_FFSSP.raw B126_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B126_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS B126.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (B126.zip)		
- rename B126.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B126_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B126_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B126_rawseadas.zip		Binary data transfer

Flight No. R126Route Date 7/9/05Take Off 10:00 GMTBag Samplers: Univac DeluxeSheet No. 1

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
178	10:06:50	10:07:23	52.2	0.9W	10,000 ft
92	10:11:00				- " -
92	10:11:19	10:11:49	52.1	1.3W	10,000 ft
50	10:15:50	10:16:20			10,000 ft
43	10:20:50	10:20:20	51.8N	2.2W	- " -
33	10:36:32	10:36:58			6,000 ft
342	10:37:35	10:38:04	51.4N	3.8W	6 - 5 x ft
475	10:39:49	10:40:20			4,000 ft
406	10:40:50	10:41:18			4 - 2 kft
129	10:43:34	10:44:02			2000 ft
600	10:44:43	10:45:12			2 - 1 kft
441	45:40	46:08			1000 ft
498	46:40	47:10			- " -
241	47:40	48:10			- " -
535	48:40	49:10			
26	49:40	50:10			
121	50:40	51:10	50.9N	4.6W	
499	51:40	52:10			
70	52:40	53:10			
93	53:40	54:10			
63	54:40	55:10			5000 ft.
99	57:40	58:10			- " -
237	11:00:40	11:01:10			- " -
408	11:03:40	11:04:10			- " -
128	11:07:10	11:07:40			2,000 ft. - 1000 ft.
392	08:10	08:40			1,000 ft
271	09:10	09:40			- " -
51	10:10	10:40	50.0N	3.4W	- " -
249	11:10	11:40			
5	12:10	12:34			
205	13:10	13:40			
381	14:10	14:40			
252	15:10	15:40			
2	16:10	16:40			
28	17:10	17:40			
172	18:10	18:40			
226	19:10	19:40			
619	20:10	20:40			
288	21:10	21:40	50.0N	2.5W	
186	22:10	22:40			
421	23:10	23:40			

Flight No. Route Date Take Off Bag Samplers: Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
102	11:24:10	11:24:40			
402	11:25:10	11:25:40	50.0N	2.1W	1000 ft
184	26:10:15	26:45			
424	27:10	27:40			
96	28:20	28:50			
385	29:10	29:40			
100	30:10	30:40			
104	31:10	31:40			
242	32:10	32:40			
528	33:10	33:40			
145	34:10	34:40			
254	35:10	35:40			
290	36:10	36:40			
95	37:10	37:40			
31	38:10	38:40			
71	39:16	39:46			
246	40:10	40:40			
106	41:17	41:47			
1	42:10	42:40			
396	43:10	43:40			
80	44:10	44:40			
87	45:10	45:40			
14	46:10	46:40			
06	47:20	47:50			
82	48:10	48:40			
140	49:10	49:40			
532	50:10	50:40			
470	51:10	51:40			
215	52:10	52:40			
209	53:10	53:40			
30	54:10	54:40			
164	55:10	55:40			
328	56:10	56:40	50.6N	0.4E	1000 ft
387	57:32	58:03			
464	58:18	58:48			
218	59:10	59:40			
339	12:00:10	12:00:40			
454	12:01:10	12:01:40			
601	12:02:10	12:02:40			
489	12:03:10	12:03:40			
265	12:04:10	12:04:40			

Flight No. Route Date Take Off Bag Samplers: Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
494	12:05:10	12:05:42	50.9N	11 E	1000ft
430	12:06:10	12:06:40			
622	07:10	07:40			
189	08:10	08:40			
250	09:10	09:40			
173	10:10	10:40			
127	11:10	11:40			
179	12:10	12:40			
625	13:10	13:40			
176	14:15	14:45			
247	15:10	15:40			
90	16:10	16:40			
244	17:10	17:40			
57	18:10	18:40			
55	19:10	19:40			
64	20:10	20:40			
180	21:10	21:40			
79	22:10	22:40			
112	23:10	23:40			
21	24:10	24:40			
399	25:10	25:40			
268	26:10	26:40			
546	27:10	27:40			
282	28:10	28:40			
493	29:10	29:40	52.3N	1.8E	1000ft
230	30:10	30:40			
53	31:10	31:40			
7	32:10	32:40			
349	33:10	33:40			
488	34:10	34:40			
8	35:10	35:40			
188	36:10	36:40			
103	37:10	37:40			
435	38:10	38:40			
496	39:10	39:40			
9	40:10	40:40			
177	41:10	41:40			
409	42:10	42:40	52.9N	1.2E	1000ft
452	43:10	43:40			
529	44:10	44:40			
263	45:10	45:40			

Flight No. Route Date Take Off Bag Samplers: Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
524	12:46:10	12:46:40	53.1N	0.9E	1000 ft
311	12:47:10	12:47:44			
42	48:10	48:40			
223	49:10	49:40			
206	50:10	50:40			
505	51:10	51:40			
393	52:10	52:40			
220	53:10	53:40			
522	54:10	54:40			
460	55:10	55:40			
503	56:10	56:40			
485	57:10	57:40			
510	58:10	58:46			
322	59:10	59:40			
256	13:00:10	13:00:40	53.8N	0.2E	1000 ft
84	13:07:10	13:07:40			
123	13:02:10	13:02:40			
56	03:10	03:40			
61	04:10	04:40			
17	05:10	05:40			
211	06:10	06:40			
74	07:10	07:40			
47	08:10	08:40			
25	09:10	09:40			
232	10:10	10:40			
478	11:10	11:40			
327	12:10	12:40			
507	13:10	13:40			
434	14:48:10	14:40			
332	15:10	15:40			
329	16:16	16:46			
132	17:10	17:40			
88	18:10	18:40			
203	19:10	19:40			
651	20:10	20:40			
187	21:10	21:40			
388	22:10	22:40			
060	23:10	23:40			
607	24:10	24:40			
338	25:10	25:40	55.0N	1.1W	
473	26:10	26:40			

Flight No. R126

Route

Date 7/9/05

Take Off 10:00

Bag Samplers: Debbie, Chicora

Sheet No. 5

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
482	13:27:10	13:27:40	55.1N	1.2W	1000ft
335	13:28:10	13:28:40			
544	29:10	29:40			
285	30:00	30:30			profile
82	30:40	31:10			-"-
89	31:40	32:10			-"-
29	32:35	33:05			-"-
236	33:45	34:15			4000ft
526	34:45	35:15			4000 - 6000ft
81	35:40	36:10			4000 - 6000ft
301	36:35	37:05			6000 - 6000ft
442	37:35	38:05			6000ft
	39:40	40:10			
484	13:48:00	13:48:30			6000 - 1000ft
245	13:49:00	13:49:30			-"-
18	50:00	50:30			1000ft
487	51:00	51:30			
136	51:53	52:23			
152	52:57	53:27			
158	53:57	54:30			
354	54:55	55:25			
83	55:55	56:27			
185	56:55	57:25			
314	57:55	58:25			
91	58:55	59:25			
160	59:55	14:00:25	54.3N	0.3W	1000ft
101	14:00:55	14:01:25			
427	14:01:55	14:02:25			
46	02:55	03:25			
611	03:55	04:25			
162	04:55	05:25			
97	05:55	06:25			
48	06:55	07:25			
451	07:55	08:25			
13	08:55	09:25			
415	09:55	10:25			
58	10:55	11:25			
126	11:55	12:25			
86	12:55	13:25			
403	13:55	14:25			

Flight No B126

CCNC LOG

Exp. Amper

Date 7/1/05

Page 1 of

ALLEVIATOR GMT		Height	Dyn	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
1010			27.9	0.48	0.69	1.04	1.38	1.96	S
				938	1161	1632	1844	2059	D
				513	497	481	481	470	B
				2485	2466	2450	2432	2414	R
				1003.2	1003.2	1003.1	1003.2	1003.1	P
				0.47	0.69	1.03	1.36	1.96	S
112730			28.1	403	418	1546	1837	3124	D
				311	308	303	301	361	B
				2322	2330	2356	2370	2392	R
				1002.6	1002.5	1002.6	1002.5	1002.5	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				0.47	0.68	1.00	1.34	1.94	S
115020			28.3	465	1721	2000	2248	3595	D
				281	278	275	289	342	B
				2453	2418	2403	2392	2381	R
				1002.6	1002.5	1002.6	1002.5	1002.5	P
				0.47	0.66	1.00	1.35	1.95	S
121700			28.2	3047	3121	3200	4095	4092	D
				360	360	371	372	372	B
				2350	2359	2364	2366	2370	R
				1002.6	1002.6	1002.6	1002.7	1002.7	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				0.47	0.64	1.00	1.29	1.92	S
124500			28.1	1883	1680	2680	3000	4092	D
				336	335	335	337	374	B
				2488	2489	2487	2482	2477	R
				1001.6	1000	1000	1000	1000	P
				0.46	0.66	1.00	1.29	1.88	S
1305			27.5	864	1394	2228	2775	3411	D
				333	330	327	327	357	B
				2400	2389	2382	2378	2372	R
				998.6	998.6	997.2	997.2	997.2	P

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT ON	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	1	2	3	4	5	REMARKS
1352				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			27.5	0.46	0.66				S
				289					D
				334	339				B
				2349	2349				R
				996	996				P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
1402				0.45	0.66	1.00	1.28	1.96	S
				1601	2080	2500	3155	4082	D
				309	314	318	318	328	B
				2470	2456	2441	2416	2408	R
				995.8	995.9	997.1	996.1	997	P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P

Scrubbed
dry
papers

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: B126
 Date: 07/09/05
 Operator: Jim Hopkins

Campaign Name: AMPEP

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
		ARCON CYLINDER PRESSURE = 184 bar Cu ₂ SO ₄ = half full. WAS cylinder pressure = ~ 54 bar. note: v. small leak on WAS cylinder. - didn't appear to drop over ~ 10 mins but noticed a drop over flight time ~ 40mins	
		TIME CHECK PAN+WAS @ 9:32	
~ 10:00	-	TAKE OFF	
~ 10:03	-	TURN ON WAS cylinder, WAS PUMP + 24V.	
~ 10:05	-	RUN 1 - 10000 ft for NOxy cal.	3.07.
10:10:16	1	Normal filling mode @ 10000ft to check WAS system is working okay.	3.06.
10:36:31		Descending to 6000 ft. for start of profile. Run 2-1 @ 6000ft	
10:37:10	2	XXXXXXXXXX Sampled @ tail end of run.	3.15
0:39:48		Run 3-1 @ 4000 ft.	
0:40:?		end of run. 3-1 start profile descent to 2000ft	

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: B1276

Date: 07/09/05

Campaign Name: AMPPEP

Operator: Jim Hopkins

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
11:20:01	8	FF @ 1000 ft.	3.31
11:26:10	9	FF @ 1000ft @ WP 45 (see map). AMS seeing some anthropogenic aerosols { - possibly shipping. }	3.30
11:34:10	10	FF @ 1000ft	3.31
11:39:45	11	FF @ 1000ft	3.31
11:41:19	—	WP 44 turning.	
11:48:10	12	FF @ 1000ft	?
11:53:10	13	FF @ 1000ft.	3.31
11:56:50	—	WP 43 turning WP 43 turning	
11:58:45	14	FF @ 1000 ft.	3.31
2:04:30	15	FF @ 1000 ft.	3.31
12:12:45	16	FF @ 1000 ft - Should be more polluted now. - sampled after WP 42.	3.31
2:21:30	17	FF @ 1000 ft.	3.31
2:29:32	18	FF @ 1000ft	3.31

WAS + PAN sampling summary

 Flight number: ...B126.....
 Date: 07/09/05
 Operator: JIM HOPKINS

Campaign Name: ...AMPEP.....

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
12:37:30	19	FF@ 1000ft.	3.31
12:39:47	20	FF@ 1000ft	3.31
12:42:16	21	FF@ 1000ft	3.31
12:43:49	22	FF@ 1000ft approaching WP 87 at plumes should finish now.	3.31
12:45:18	—	WP 87 turning.	—
12:50:41	23	FF @ 1000ft.	3.31
12:57:30	24	FF @ 1000ft	?
13:01:56	25	FF @ 1000ft = CO plume + SO ₂	3.31
13:04:25		WP 80	
13:09:45	26	FF@ 1000ft - high NO _x	3.31
		*Decided to extend flight path beyond 79 to reach cleaner air.	
13:21:00	27	FF@ 1000ft - passing over WP 79.	3.31

WAS sampling summary

Flight number: ...B128.....

Date: 07/09/05

Campaign Name: ...AMPEP.....

Operator: JIM HOPKINS

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
13:29:10	28	FF@ 1000 ft - began ascent at tail end of sampling.	3.31
	—	as ascend to 2000 ft	—
	—	Run @ 2000 ft for 1 min.	—
13:31:42	—	ascend to 4000 ft. (profile 5)	—
13:33:45	—	Run 8.1 @ 4000 ft. for 1 min.	—
	—	turning around before recommencing profile	—
13:36:31	—	ascend to 6000 ft (profile 6)	—
13:38:31	29	Run 9.1 @ 6000 ft FF	~3.16.
13:41:47	—	End of run 9.1	—
	—	Descend to 1000 ft to return to WP 87. before returning to Cranfield.	—
13:50:20	—	Run 10.1 @ 1000 ft - just south of WP 79.	—
13:54:00	30	FF@ 1000 ft - middlesbrough plume?	?
14:07:10	31	FF@ 1000 ft - just south of WP 80	3.31
14:20:30	32	FF@ 1000 ft.	3.32
14:25:		End of run.	

WAS sampling summary

Flight number: BIZ6
 Date: 07/09/05
 Operator: JIM HOPKINS

Campaign Name: AMPEP

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
		ascend to FL 100. (10000 ft) for NOxy cal.	
		WAS cylinder final pressure \approx 58 bar. turned off cylinder. turned off pump + 24V	
14:43		Air sample pipes closed.	
		ARGON CYLINDER TURNED OFF FINAL PRESSURE \approx 180 BAR.	

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 126

Date: 07 Sep 05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS	y	N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	Y	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	Y	Y
Heimann	n		HVPS	N	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC	Y	Y			
FWVS		N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	N	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	N
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ JO1D	Y	Y	AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	N	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO2	Y	Y	Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	N
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	Y
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	Y
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	Y
WAS	Y	y	Tube Sampling	Y	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B126

Date: 07/sep/05

Instruments

1. Upper Pyrgeometer – Zero signal following radiance signal channel.
2. Outboard video recorder – jammed tape – recovered 08/sep/05

Aircraft

1. Intercom, Flight Managers box – no repeat of previous problem
2. only one headset on core console

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B126:

Log	Reason
NOxy	No log is ever taken for NOxy
PTrMS	No log is ever taken for PTrMS
Peroxide	No log is ever taken for Peroxide

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

5 x Forward Facing Cameras
1 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Eiko Nemitz

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